

Uranium(VI) and Uranium(IV) — Two Special Types of Hard Acceptors and an Implication of this Property on Their Nature of Bonding with Different Nucleophiles

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A HRLAND, Chatt and Davis¹ tried to provide a fairly coherent picture by classifying different elements of the periodic table, in their normal oxidation states, according to their properties as 'a type', 'b type' or 'borderline' ions based on only qualitative and in some cases semiquantitative ideas. The actinides were kept outside the scope though the profile resulted out of their attempt clearly indicated that the actinides in their normal oxidation states should behave as 'a type' ions. However, Pearson² in an attempt to classify Lewis acid, showed that both UO_2^{2+} and U^{4+} ions behave as 'a type' or hard acceptors. But because of the scanty data available then none ever emphasised that the actinide ions in their higher oxidation states might behave as a special type of 'hard acid'.

During the last few years, the present authors and their collaborators³⁻¹¹ isolated and characterized a large number of dioxouranium(VI) and uranium(IV) complexes formed of neutral unidentate ligands from different physicochemical studies, such as, IR, visible and U.V. spectra, magnetic susceptibility measurements and conductance studies in solution. From such studies they conclude that both UO_2^{2+} and U^{4+} ions behave as a special type of electrophile because of a large number of vacant d- as also f-orbitals, in their valence shell, which are easily accessible for bond formation. Lanthanides, where the f-orbitals being merely low-energy inner orbitals are inaccessible chemically, simply behave as ordinary hard acids in their normal oxidation states.

According to Chatt¹², the class 'a' acids have tightly held outer electrons, but also have available empty orbitals, not too high in energy, on the metal ion. In his π -bonding theory, he emphasises that the basic atoms such as oxygen and fluorine, in particular, can form π -bonds in the opposite sense, by

donating electrons from the ligand to the empty orbitals of the metal over and above the dative σ bond which they originally form with the metal ions in question. However, this type of bonding lacks 'synergic stabilization' of the soft-soft interaction. The present authors here take the liberty of proposing that the hard-hard interaction which according to Klopman¹³ is a 'Charge-Controlled effect' when considered from the angle that there is considerable amount of $\text{L} \rightarrow \text{M} \sigma$ as also $\text{L} \rightarrow \text{M} \pi$ overlap some 'Frontier Controlled effect' are automatically involved therein inducing some covalency to the hard acid hard base complexes. That is why CrO_2Cl_2 and even UO_2Cl_2 and similarly many other such complexes have considerable covalent character and are soluble in organic solvents even though they are weakly polar. Conceptually, of course, we are considering two different theories together.

At this point it seems pertinent to discuss the electronic structure of dioxouranium(VI) ion—a most stable and most widely studied species with uranium in the hexavalent state. It has been postulated^{14,15} that the vacant orbitals of uranium (5f and 6d) remain so after the formation of four ordinary covalent bonds as $\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O}$ and even after the interaction with other ligands (termed as 'secondary ligands') in a plane perpendicular to $\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O}$ axis. Thus there is the possibility of the unshared electron pairs of oxygen atoms being further drifted towards the vacant orbitals of uranium and thereby increasing the multiplicity of uranium—oxygen bond beyond two. That is why the U-O distance in UO_2^{2+} ion is very short and close to the $\text{M}=\text{O}$ distance of lighter metals, despite the larger size of the uranium atom.

From the above discussion, the reaction between U^{6+} and O_2^{2-} ion in forming UO_2^{2+} species appears to be a typical hard-hard interaction according to

Chatt¹². But, after such extensive delocalization of electrons from oxygen to uranium (nearly one dative σ bond and two dative π bonds, all from O \rightarrow U) it may be expected that some soft character develops at the uranium centre. But the reactions of UO_2^{2+} with different secondary ligands do not give any evidence of such behaviour. It always refuses to furnish any stable complex with soft nucleophiles like R_3P , R_3As or R_2S but rather prefers to combine with the hard site of ambident nucleophiles^{5,6,8} like, NCS^- , R_2SO , etc.

An attempt³⁻⁴ to force interactions between uranyl(VI) salts with a typical soft base, triphenyl phosphine, gives interesting results. In nitrogen atmosphere no product is isolated and when the experiment is conducted in the presence of air only $\text{UO}_2\text{X}_2 \cdot 2\text{Ph}_3\text{PO}$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$ and NO_3), a hard-hard complex is formed. Even the effect of 'symbiosis'¹⁶ does not work, since UO_2I_2 also does not form any adduct with soft bases. Thus even after such extensive flow of electron over uranium in the UO_2^{2+} ion—its hardness still more than compensates the 'symbiotic effect'.

From the trend of the elements in the periodic table it can be said that some soft character should have developed over uranium, in view of the structure of UO_2^{2+} ion discussed. When one goes down from $3d^n$ to $4d^n$ to $5d^n$ keeping a particular oxidation state fixed and hence the electronic arrangement the same, the polarizability and so the softness increases and in the heavier elements dispersion force wins over the electrostatic forces, in their interactions with different nucleophiles (compare Ni^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Pt^{2+} ; Mn^{2+} , Re^{2+} ; Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , etc.). But this effect is never found in UO_2^{2+} ion. There are several reasons to believe that it is even harder than MoO_2^{2+} and WO_2^{2+} ion. It may be due to the fact that apart from the vacant d orbitals as in the case of the transitional elements, this actinide species, in the said oxidation state, has all the vacant and chemically accessible f-orbitals. It is perhaps this aspect which makes the uranyl(VI) ion a *special type* of hard acid. We may venture to say that similar type of hard character may be found in NpO_2^{3+} , PuO_2^{4+} and even in NpO_2^{2+} and PuO_2^{2+} ions.

When uranyl(VI) ion reacts with secondary ligands and electrons from the latter occupy vacant uranium orbitals then oxygen to uranium dative π bonding in the UO_2^{2+} ion is affected depending on the donor ability of the said ligands. This decreases the multiplicity of the U—O bonds in the oxocation. Particularly the oxygen $2p \rightarrow$ uranium $5f$ dative π -bonding

(which actually increases the multiplicity of U—O bonds beyond two) is very much sensitive to the donor ability of equatorial ligands as is evidenced by the mode of the change of ν_3 (asymmetric stretching frequency) of the said oxocation with the change of such ligands^{7,17}. Other type of oxocations, where there is no such vacant and accessible f-orbitals, are not so much sensitive to the donor ability of other ligands. This is a special property of the oxo actinide ions in their higher oxidation states.

Moreover, it has been found^{18,7} that even in the ground state where $S=0$, the uranyl ion exhibits feeble paramagnetism due to the large f-orbital contribution¹⁸. That the largest contribution comes from the two $5f$ σ -bonding electrons is calculated from the relation $16N\alpha\beta^2/\Delta$, where N is the Avogadro number, β is the Bohr Magneton, α is the probability that the bonding electron is in the uranium $5f$ states (as opposed to being located on an oxygen atom) and Δ is the energy required to promote a $5f$ σ -bonding electron to a $5f$ π state. Since the multiplicity of uranium oxygen bond, as mentioned earlier, depends on the extent of dative π -bonding from the filled oxygen orbitals to the empty $5f$ orbitals of uranium, it is obvious that like the χ_M of UO_2^{2+} ion, the multiplicity and hence the force constant of the U—O bond is directly proportional to the value of α . The present authors first compared the χ_M and ν_3 of the UO_2^{2+} ion in a large number of complexes isolated by them and found quite interesting results as recorded in the table⁷. It has been found that in the quinoline N-oxide complexes the said parameters decrease in the order as $\text{Br}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{NCS}^-$. Such behaviour arises from the electronic interaction of anionic ligands with the uranyl ion which being a predominantly hard acid prefers to combine with a predominantly hard base as isothiocyanate ($-\text{NCS}^-$) and so it prefers Cl^- to Br^- ion. Similar trend is observed in sulphoxide complexes. However, straightforward comparison among different series is difficult as then the vibrational interaction of Jones¹⁹ will have to be applied. Again, if both the factors are applied the resulting frequency will be unpredictable. In this connection it may be mentioned that in the sulphoxide series the comparatively lower χ_M and ν_3 values of the UO_2^{2+} ion in the complex $\text{UO}_2 \cdot \text{Br}_2 \cdot 3\text{Ph}_2\text{SO}$ is due to the greater extent of electron transfer to the uranium atom from the three sulphoxide ligands than that achieved from two such ligands in chloride and nitrate complexes.

In the cationic complexes, viz, $[\text{UO}_2(\text{Ph}_2\text{SO})_5]^{2+}$ and $[\text{UO}_2(\text{Ph}_3\text{PO})_4]^{2+}$, according to the electronic

TABLE

Compound	χ_M of $UO_2^{2+} \times 10^6$ e.m.u.	Asymmetric stretching frequency (ν_3) of UO_2^{2+} (cm^{-1})	K_{eff} (U-O) m.dynes/A.
$UO_2Cl_2 \cdot 2QO^*$	104	910	7.55
$UO_2Br_2 \cdot 2QO$	191	920	7.72
$UO_2(NCS)_2 \cdot 3QO$	42	904	7.39
$UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2QO$	172	912	7.56
$UO_2Cl_2 \cdot 2Ph_2SO$	215	930	7.87
$UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2Ph_2SO$	232	935	7.96
$UO_2Br_2 \cdot 3Ph_2SO$	170	920	7.72
$[UO_2(Ph_2SO)_6](ClO_4)_2$	211	930	7.87
$[UO_2(Ph_3PO)_4](ClO_4)_2$	147	—	—
$UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2(PhO)_3PO$	163	950	—
$(Ph_3PH)_2UO_2Cl_4$	90	906	—
$(Ph_3PH)_2UO_2Br_4$	94	918	—

*QO=quinoline N-oxide.

trality principle, the accumulation of negative charge over the uranium atom due to the electron transfer from the equatorial ligands is markedly reduced because of the distribution of two units of positive charges throughout all the atoms in the complexes. The magnitude of such a positive charge distribution is to a marked extent over the uranium atom because of its low electronegativity value. This is expected to augment the α -values and hence the susceptibility and the force constant of U-O bonds of the UO_2^{2+} ion in the cationic complexes mentioned. An exactly opposite situation is predicted for the anionic complexes, viz, $[UO_2Cl_4]^{2-}$ and $[UO_2Br_4]^{2-}$ and confirmed experimentally from the data in the table.

It is now apparent that whenever uranium(VI) manages to get maximum electron density over it to reduce its hard acid character to some extent, it immediately refuses to accept 'extra' π -electron density from oxygen 2p to its own 5f orbital to maintain its "intrinsic hardness".

The situation in uranium(IV) is also quite interesting. There is enough spectroscopic evidence

to suggest that it has the $5f^2$ configuration in the ground state and f-f transition spectra has been recorded by a number of workers^{20,21} including the present authors²². But uranium(IV) refuses to react with soft nucleophiles^{4,20} like R_3P , R_2S , etc. Analogous $5d^2$ case, say for instance Re(V) affords very stable solid adducts like, $ReOX_3 \cdot 2Ph_3P$ ²³ in a variety of isomeric forms. This clearly indicates that in $5d^2$ case, Re(V), some amount of soft electrophillic character is developed but that is never found in $5f^2$ case as in U(IV). This is, again because, in uranium, vacancy of both d and f orbitals makes it a different type of acceptor—a very different type, even in its tetravalent state where already two f-electrons exist in its valence orbital.

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